

BODY WEIGHT IN DIFFERENT CATEGORIES OF HYPERGLYCEMIA

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Abstract: This report presents the results of a study of body weight in patients with impaired glucose tolerance and type 2 diabetes mellitus. A representative sample of the unorganized male population was examined at the age of 40-69 years. A total of 894 people were examined. Analysis of the state of glycemia was carried out on the basis of indicators of the standard glucose tolerance test. A positive association of body weight with type 2 diabetes mellitus and impaired glucose tolerance was established. At the same time, it has been shown that in individuals with normal levels of glycemic, the average Quetelet index levels are within the limits corresponding to the criteria for overweight. The conclusion is made about the expediency of continuing research to study the pathogenesis of overweight comorbidity and hyperglycemia.

Keywords: overweight, obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, impaired glucose tolerance, comorbidity.

Relevance. Trends in the prevalence of overweight and obesity in different countries are mixed. In most countries, the prevalence of overweight and obesity is increasing [1]. The main risk factors include poor nutrition, inactivity, stress, and others [2]. Many studies have linked obesity and overweight to diabetes mellitus and metabolic syndrome [3]. The association of obesity with various risk factors, mortality, and reproductive function in women has been established [4,5]. To prevent the formation and progression of obesity and being overweight, it is necessary to take measures for the timely diagnosis and elimination of risk factors. One of the factors closely associated with obesity is such categories of hyperglycemia as type 2 diabetes mellitus and impaired glucose tolerance (IGT).

Research objective: to study the state of body weight among individuals with different categories of glycemia.

Material and methods. A group of 894 men, who were between 30 and 69 years old at the time of the survey, was examined. This group was a representative sample of the unorganized population. The topic of weight was

studied according to WHO criteria based on the Quetelet index indicator (QI) [6]. A standard glucose tolerance test was performed to study glycemia. Type 2 diabetes mellitus and IGT were detected according to the criteria of the American Diabetes Association [7]. Statistical processing was performed using the following programs: "MedCalc" and Microsoft Excel-16.

Research results. The study showed that the average values of QI have the lowest values in the group of people with normal glucose tolerance (Table 1). In the group with IGT, the QI value is slightly higher than in those with normal glycemic levels. Even greater differences were found between the average QI levels among individuals with normal glycemic levels and in the group of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Table 1.

Average values of the Quetelet index in different categories of hyperglycemia

Categories of hyperglycemia	Normal tolerance level	IGT	DM type 2
N	539	329	26
Average	25,664	26,334 **	29,308 ***
Median value	26,000	26,000	28,500
SD	3,7536	4,2409	3,9168
RSD	0,1463	0,1610	0,1336
SEM	0,1617	0,2338	0,7682
P		<0,01	<0,001

Note: the table shows the reliability of differences in indicators relative to groups with normal glucose tolerance

In absolute terms, these differences seem insignificant. However, statistical analysis indicates that these differences are not random. The reliability of the compared indicators was high. This is explained by the fact that the degree of reliability of differences between indicators is determined not only by the magnitude of the differences themselves but also by other factors. With relatively small differences in the values of the studied indicators, the degree of reliability of these differences can be high. Such results can be obtained under

the following conditions: if a large sample is analyzed, there is a slight variance in the data, and the significance level is correctly selected.

At the same time, in individuals with normal glycemic indices, the average QI levels were in the range of 25.664 ± 3.7536 . According to the current classification, QI indicators are >25 and <30 indicate that the patient is overweight. Therefore, based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that among individuals with normal levels of glycemia, there are other risk factors other than hyperglycemia. At the same time, these data may indicate the priority of weight gain in the process of comorbidity with hyperglycemia.

Conclusions

1. In patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and individuals with impaired glucose tolerance, the average Quetelet index levels are significantly higher than in individuals with normal glycemic levels. This fact indicates that latent hyperglycemia in the form of impaired glucose tolerance may be a risk factor for obesity.

2. The presence of excess body weight among individuals with normal glycemic indices suggests that they have other risk factors other than hyperglycemia. These data suggest the feasibility of continuing research on the pathogenesis of comorbidity of weight gain with hyperglycemia.

References:

1. NCD Risk Factor Collaboration (NCD-RisC) (2024). Worldwide trends in underweight and obesity from 1990 to 2022: a pooled analysis of 3663 population-representative studies with 222 million children, adolescents, and adults. *Lancet* (London, England), 403(10431), 1027–1050. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(23\)02750-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(23)02750-2)
2. Lee KX, Quek KF, Ramadas A. Dietary and Lifestyle Risk Factors of Obesity Among Young Adults: A Scoping Review of Observational Studies. *Curr Nutr Rep*. 2023 Dec;12(4):733-743. doi: 10.1007/s13668-023-00513-9. Epub 2023 Dec 1. PMID: 38038894.
3. Chandrasekaran P, Weiskirchen R. The Role of Obesity in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus-An Overview. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2024 Feb 4;25(3):1882. doi: 10.3390/ijms25031882. PMID: 38339160; PMCID: PMC10855901.
4. Kayumov U.K., Kalandarova U.A., Ibadova M.U., Ismatova M.N. The formation of a hard «end points» for various risk factors /*Journal of Biomedicine and Practice*, 2019, vol. 1, issue 1, pp. 79–84.
5. Kayumov U. K., Matmuratova S. O., Khatamova D. T., Saipova M. L., and Musaeva Sh. Z. 2023. "Metabolic Syndrome in Women of Childbearing Age State of the Main Components". *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science* 4

- (5), 959-63.
<https://cajmns.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJMNS/article/view/1948>.
6. Weir CB, Jan A. BMI Classification Percentile And Cut Off Points. [Updated 2023 Jun 26]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK541070/>
7. American Diabetes Association Professional Practice Committee; 2. Diagnosis and Classification of Diabetes: Standards of Care in Diabetes—2024. *Diabetes Care* 1 January 2024; 47 (Supplement_1): S20–S42. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc24-S002>